

GENERALIZATION OF L-FUZZY COUNTABLE COMPACT SPACES

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Abstract:

By means of γ -open L-sets and their inequality, countable γ -compactness and γ -Lindelof property are introduced in L- topological spaces, where L is a complete De Morgan algebra. They do not depend on the structure of basis lattice L and L does not require any distributivity. An L-set is γ -compact if and only if it is countably γ - compact and has the γ - Lindelof property.

1. Introduction:

It is known that compactness and its stronger and weaker forms play very important roles in topology. Based on fuzzy topological spaces introduced by Chang [2], various kinds of fuzzy compactness [2, 5, 11] have been established. However, these concepts of fuzzy compactness rely on the structure of L and L is required to be completely distributive. In [10], for a complete De Morgan algebra L, Shi introduced a new definition of fuzzy compactness in L-topological spaces using open L-sets and their inequality. This new definition does not depend on the structure of L. In this paper, by means of γ -open L-sets and their inequality, countable γ -compactness and γ -Lindelof property are introduced in L-topological spaces, where L is a complete De Morgan algebra. They do not depend on the structure of basis lattice L and L does not require any distributivity. An L-set is γ -compact if and only if it is countably γ -compact and has the γ - Lindelof property.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper, $(L, \vee, \wedge, ')$ is a complete De Morgan algebra, X a nonempty set and L^X the set of all L –fuzzy sets (or L-sets for short) on X. The smallest element and the largest element in L^X are denoted by $\underline{0}$ and $\underline{1}$. An element a in L is called a prime element if $b \wedge c \leq a$ implies that $b \leq a$ or $c \leq a$. a in L is called a co-prime element if a' is a prime element [4]. The set of nonunit prime elements in L is denoted by $P(L)$ and the set of nonzero co-prime elements in L by $M(L)$. The binary relation ∞ in L is defined as follows; for $a, b \in L, a \infty b$ if and only if for every subset $D \subseteq L$, the relation $b \leq \sup D$ always implies the existence of $d \in D$ with $a \leq d$ [3]. In a completely distributive De Morgan algebra L, each element b is a supof $\{a \in L \mid a \infty b\}$. The set $\beta(b) = \{a \in L \mid a \infty b\}$ is called the greatest minimal family of b in the sense of [5,11]. Now, for $b \in L$, we define $\beta^*(b) = \beta(b) \cap M(L), \alpha(b) = \{A \in L^X \mid a' \infty b\}$ and $\alpha^*(b) = \alpha(b) \cap P(L)$. For $a \in L$ and $A \in L^X$, we write $A^{(\alpha)} = \{x \in X \mid A(x) \leq \alpha\}$ and $A_{(\alpha)} = \{x \in X \mid \alpha \in \beta(A(x))\}$ and for a subfamily $\psi \subseteq L^X$, $2(\psi)$, (resp. $2^{(\psi)}$) will denote the set of all finite (countable) subfamilies of ψ . A L-topological space is an ordered pair (X, τ) , where τ is a subfamily of L^X which contains $\underline{0}, \underline{1}$ and is closed for any suprema and finite infima. An L-topological space is an ordered triple (X, τ) , where τ is a subfamily of L^X which contains $\underline{0}, \underline{1}$, and is closed for any suprema and finite infima.

Definition 2.1 [5, 11]: For a topological space (X, τ) let $\omega_L(\tau)$ denote the family of all the lower semi continuous maps from (X, τ) to L; that is, $\omega_L(\tau) = \{A \in L^X \mid A^{(\alpha)} \in \tau, \alpha \in L\}$. Then $\omega_L(\tau)$ is an L-topology on X and $(X, \omega_L(\tau))$ is topologically generated by (X, τ) .

Definition 2.2 [5, 11]: An L-topological space (X, τ) is weak induced if, for all $\alpha \in L$ and for all $A \in \tau$, it follows that $A^{(\alpha)} \in \tau$, where $[\tau]$ denotes the topology formed by all crisp sets in τ . It is obvious that $(X, \omega_L(\tau))$ is weak induced.

Definition 2.3 [9]: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $\alpha \in L \setminus \{1\}$, and $A \in L^X$. A family $\mu \subseteq L^X$ is called

1. an α -shading of A if for any $x \in X, (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \leq \alpha$.
2. a strong α -shading of A if $\bigwedge_{\beta \in \mu} A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \mu} B(x) \leq \alpha$.
3. an R-neighborhood family of A if for any $x \in X, (A(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \geq \alpha$.
4. a strong α -R neighbourhood family of A if $\bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \geq \alpha$.

It is obvious that strong α -shading of A is an α -shading of A , an strong α -R-neighbourhood family of A if an α -R-neighbourhood family of A if and only if μ 's an strong α -shading of A .

Definition 2.4 [9]: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and $A \in L^X$. A family $\mu \subseteq L^X$ is called

1. $\alpha\beta_\alpha$ -cover of A if for any $x \in X$, it follows that $\alpha \in \beta(A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x))$.
2. a strong β_α -cover of A if $\alpha \in \beta(\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x)))$.
3. αQ_α -cover of A if for any $x \in X$, it follows that $A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x) \geq \alpha$.

It is obvious that an $S\text{-}\beta_\alpha$ -cover of A be a β_α -cover of A , and $\alpha\beta_\alpha$ -cover of A must be Q_α -cover of A .

Definition 2.5 [9]: Let $A \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and $A \in L^X$. A family $\mu \subseteq L^X$ is said to have weak α -nonempty intersection in A if $\bigvee_{x \in X} A(x) \wedge \beta(x) \geq \alpha$. μ is said to have the finite weak α -intersection property in A if every finite subfamily ν of μ has weak α -nonempty intersection in A .

Lemma 2.6: Let L be a complete Heyting algebra, $f: X \rightarrow Y$ a map and $f\vec{L}: L^X \rightarrow L^Y$ the extension of f . Then for any family $\psi \subseteq L^Y$, $\bigvee_{y \in Y} (f\vec{L}(A)(y) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \psi} B(y)) = \bigvee_{x \in X} (A(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \psi} B(f(x)))$.

Definition 2.7 [1]: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $a \in L^X$. Then A is called a - γ open set if $A \leq \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A)) \vee \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$. The complement of an γ -open set is called an γ -closed set. Also, $\gamma O(L^X)$ and $\gamma C(L^X)$ will always denote the family of all γ -open sets and γ -closed sets respectively. Obviously, $A \in O(L^X)$ if and only if $A' \in \gamma C(L^X)$.

Definition 2.8 [1]: Let (L^X, τ) be an L-topological space, $A, B \in L^X$. Let $\gamma \text{Int}(A) = \bigvee \{ B \in L^X \mid B \leq A, B \in \gamma C(L^X) \}$, $\gamma \text{Cl}(A) = \bigwedge \{ B \in L^X \mid A \leq B, B \in \gamma C(L^X) \}$. Then $\gamma \text{Int}(A)$ and $\gamma \text{Cl}(A)$ are called the γ -interior and γ -closure of A , respectively.

Definition 2.9 [6]: Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two L-topological spaces. A map $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called

1. γ -continuous if $f\vec{L}(B)$ is γ -open in (Y, σ) for every $B \in \tau$.
2. γ -irresolute if $f\vec{L}(B)$ is γ -open in (Y, σ) for every γ -open L-set B in (X, τ) .

Definition 2.10 [7]: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ is called γ -compact if for every family μ of γ -open L-sets, it follows that

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \leq \bigvee_{\nu \in 2(\mu)} \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \nu} B(x)).$$

(X, τ) is called γ -compact if $\underline{1}$ is γ -compact.

3. Properties of Countable γ -Compactness:

Definition 3.1: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ is called countable γ -compact if for every family μ of γ -open L-sets, it follows that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \leq \bigvee_{\nu \in 2(\mu)} \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \nu} B(x))$. Then (X, τ) is called countable γ -compact if $\underline{1}$ is countable γ -compact.

Definition 3.2: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ is said to have the γ -Lindelof property if for every family μ of γ -open L-sets, it follows that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \leq \bigvee_{\nu \in 2(\mu)} \bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{\beta \in \nu} B(x))$. Then (X, τ)

have the γ -Lindelof property if $\underline{1}$ have the γ -Lindelof property. Obviously, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 3.3: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ γ -compact if and only if A is countably γ -compact and has the γ -Lindelof property.

Theorem 3.4: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ is countably γ -compact if and only if for every family μ of γ -closed L-sets, it follows that $\bigvee_{x \in X} (A'(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{\nu \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (A'(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \nu} B(x))$.

Proof: This is immediate from Definition 3.1 and quasi complements.

Theorem 3.5: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space. $A \in L^X$ has the γ -Lindelof property if and only if for every family μ of γ -closed L-sets, it follows that

$$\bigvee_{x \in X} (A'(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \mu} B(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{\nu \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (A'(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{\beta \in \nu} B(x)).$$

Proof: This is immediate from Definition 3.2 and quasi complements.

Theorem 3.6: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $A \in L^X$. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

1. A is countably γ -compact
2. For any $a \in L \setminus \{1\}$, each countably γ -open strong α -shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α -shading of A .
3. For any $a \in L \setminus \{0\}$ each countably γ -closed strong α -R- q neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α -R- q neighbourhood family of A .

4. For any $a \in L \setminus \{0\}$, each countably family of γ -closed L-sets which has the finite weak α - intersection property in A has weakly α -nonempty intersection in A.

Theorem 3.7: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $A \in L^X$. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

1. A has the γ -Lindelof property
2. For any $a \in L \setminus \{1\}$, each γ -open strong α - shading μ of A has a countably subfamily which is an strong a -shading of A.
3. For any $a \in L \setminus \{0\}$, each countable γ -closed strong α - R- q neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α - R- neighbourhood family of A.
4. For any $a \in L \setminus \{0\}$, each countable family of γ -closed L-sets which has the finite weak α - intersection property in A has weakly α -nonempty intersection in A.

Theorem 3.8: Let L be a complete Heyting algebra. If both C and D are countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof), then $C \vee D$ is countable γ -compact (γ -Lindelof).

Proof: We only prove that the theorem is true for countable γ -compactness. By Theorem 3.5, for any family μ of γ -closed L-sets, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee_{x \in X} ((C \vee D)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) &= \{ \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \} \vee \{ \bigvee_{x \in X} (D(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \} \\ &\geq \{ \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \} \vee \{ \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (D(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \} \\ &= \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (C \vee D)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x). \end{aligned}$$

This shows that $C \vee D$ is countably γ -compact.

Theorem 3.9: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $C, D \in L^X$. If C is countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof) and D is γ -closed, then $C \wedge D$ is countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof).

Proof: We only prove that the theorem is true for countable γ -compactness. By Theorem 3.5, for any family μ of γ -closed L-sets, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee_{x \in X} ((C \wedge D)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) &= \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu \cup \{D\}} B(x)) \\ &\geq \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu \cup \{D\})} \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \\ &\geq \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \wedge \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu \cup \{D\})} \bigvee_{x \in X} (C(x) \wedge D(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \\ &= \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} ((C \wedge D)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \end{aligned}$$

This shows that $C \wedge D$ is countably γ -compact.

Theorem 3.10: Let L be a complete Heyting algebra and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a γ -irresolute map. If A is a countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof) L-set in (X, τ) , then $f \bar{L}(A)$ is an countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof) L-set in (Y, σ) .

Proof: We only prove that the theorem is true for countably γ -compact. Suppose that μ is a countable family of

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee_{y \in Y} f \bar{L}(A)(y) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(y) &= \bigvee_{x \in X} ((A)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} f \bar{L}(B)(x)) \\ &= \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{x \in X} ((A)(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} f \bar{L}(B)(x)) = \bigwedge_{v \in 2(\mu)} \bigvee_{y \in Y} f \bar{L}(A)(y) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \mu} B(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f \bar{L}(A)$ is countably γ -compact.

Analogously, we have the following result.

Theorem 3.11: Let L be a complete Heyting algebra and $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \tau)$ be an γ -continuous map. If A is a countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof) L-set in (X, τ) , then $f \bar{L}(A)$ is an countably γ -compact (Lindelof) L-set in (Y, τ) .

Now, we assume that L is a completely distributive de Morgan algebra.

Theorem 3.12: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space and $A \in L^X$. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

1. A is countably γ compact.
2. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
3. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
4. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \in \beta(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an S-b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
5. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \in \beta(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is a b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
6. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
7. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a finite subfamily which is an α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
8. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an S-b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
9. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an α b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
10. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, each countably γ open strong α shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α -shading of A.
11. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, each countably γ open strong α shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an α -shading of A.
12. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, and any countably γ open strong α shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν is an strong S-b shading of A.
13. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, and any countably γ open strong α shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in \alpha(\alpha)$ such that ν is α b shading of A.
14. For any $\alpha \in P(L)$, each countably γ open strong α shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α shading of A.
15. For any $\alpha \in P(L)$, each countably γ open strong α shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an strong α shading of A.
16. For any $\alpha \in P(L)$, and any countably γ open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in \alpha^*(\alpha)$ such that ν is an S-b-shading of A.
17. For any $\alpha \in P(L)$, and any countably γ open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in \alpha^*(\alpha)$ such that ν is a S-b-shading of A.
18. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any countably γ open α -shading μ open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an S- β_α -cover of A.
19. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any countably γ open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is α β_α -cover of A.
20. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any countably γ open S- β_α -cover μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in L$ with $\alpha \in \beta(b)$ such that ν is an S- β_α cover of A.
21. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any countably γ open S- β_α -cover μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in L$ with $\alpha \in \beta(b)$ such that ν is α S- β_α cover of A.

22. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$, each countably γ open $S-\beta_\alpha$ cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an $S-\beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
23. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$, each countably γ open $S-\beta_\alpha$ cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is $\alpha \beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
24. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ and any countably γ open $S-\beta_\alpha -$ cover μ of A , there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in M(L)$ with $\alpha \in \beta^*(b) -$ such that ν is an $S-\beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
25. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ and any countably γ open $S-\beta_\alpha -$ cover μ of A , there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \in M(L)$ with $\alpha \in \beta^*(b)$ such that ν is $\alpha \beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
26. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ open $Q_\alpha -$ cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is αQ_b cover of A .
27. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ - open $Q_\alpha -$ cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is αQ_b cover of A .
28. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ - open $Q_\alpha -$ cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is $\alpha S-\beta_b$ cover of A .
29. For any $A \in M(L)$, and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each countably γ open Q_α cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is a Q_b cover of A .
30. For any $A \in M(L)$ and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each countably γ open Q_α cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is a Q_b cover of A .
31. For any $A \in M(L)$ and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each countably γ open Q_α cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is a $S-\beta_b$ cover of A .

Proof: (1) $\Rightarrow$ (2) : This follows directly from Theorem 3.7

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (3) : This is easy to prove if one notices that every strong $\alpha - R -$ neighbourhood family of A is an $\alpha - R -$ neighbourhood family of A .

(3) $\Rightarrow$ (4): Let $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and ψ is a countably γ closed strong $\alpha - R -$ neighbourhood family of A . Then $\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \psi} B(x)) \not\leq \alpha$. Take $c \in \beta(\alpha)$ such that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A(x) \wedge \bigwedge_{B \in \psi} B(x)) \not\leq c$. Obviously ψ is an γ closed $S-c-R-$ neighbourhood family of A . By (3) we know that ψ has a finite subfamily ϕ which is a $c-R-$ neighbourhood family of A . Take $b \in \beta(\alpha)$ such that $c \in \beta(b)$, then ϕ is an $S-b-R-$ neighbourhood family of A .

(4) $\Rightarrow$ (5) $\Rightarrow$ (2): Obvious.

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (7) $\Rightarrow$ (8) $\Rightarrow$ (9) $\Rightarrow$ (1) : the proof is similar.

(1) $\Leftrightarrow$ (10) : This follows directly from Theorem 3.7

(10) $\Leftrightarrow$ (11) : This is easy to prove if one notices that every strong $\alpha -$ shading of A is an α -shading of A .

(11) $\Leftrightarrow$ (12) : Let $\alpha \in L \setminus \{1\}$ and μ be a countably γ open strong $\alpha -$ shading of A . Then

$$\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \not\leq \alpha. \text{ Take } c \in \alpha(a)$$

such that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} (A'(x) \vee \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x)) \not\leq c$. Obviously μ is an γ -open $S-c-$ shading of A . By (11) we know that μ has a finite subfamily ν which is a c -shading of A . Take $b \in \alpha(a)$ such that $c \in \alpha(b)$, then ν is an $S-b-$ shading of A .

(12) $\Rightarrow$ (13) $\Rightarrow$ (10): Obvious

(10) $\Rightarrow$ (14) $\Rightarrow$ (15) $\Rightarrow$ (16) $\Rightarrow$ (17) $\Rightarrow$ (10): We can prove these in the similar way. Similarly we can prove the other results.

Theorem 3.13: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space and $A \in L^X$. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

1. A has the γ -Lindelof property.

2. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a countable subfamily which is an strong α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
3. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a countable finite subfamily which is an α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
4. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each countably γ closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \varepsilon \beta(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an S-b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
5. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \varepsilon \beta(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is a b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
6. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$ each γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a countable subfamily which is an strong α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
7. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$ and any γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A has a countable subfamily which is an α -R-neighbourhood family of A.
8. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$ and any γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \varepsilon \beta^*(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an S-b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
9. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$ and any γ -closed strong α -R-neighbourhood family ψ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ϕ of ψ and $b \varepsilon \beta^*(\alpha)$ such that ϕ is an α b-R-neighbourhood family of A.
10. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, each γ -open strong α -shading μ of A has a countable subfamily which is an strong α -shading of A.
11. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, each γ -open strong α -shading μ of A has a finite subfamily which is an α -shading of A.
12. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, and any γ -open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon \alpha(a)$ such that ν is an S-b-shading of A.
13. For any $\alpha \mathcal{L} \setminus \{1\}$, and any γ -open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a finite subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon \alpha(\alpha)$ such that ν is α b shading of A.
14. For any $\alpha \varepsilon P(L)$, each γ -open strong α -shading μ of A has a countable subfamily which is an strong α -shading of A.
15. For any $\alpha \varepsilon P(L)$, each γ -open strong α -shading μ of A has a countable subfamily which is an strong α -shading of A.
16. For any $\alpha \varepsilon P(L)$, and any γ -open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon \alpha^*(\alpha)$ such that ν is an S-b-shading of A.
17. For any $\alpha \varepsilon P(L)$, and any γ -open strong α -shading μ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon \alpha^*(\alpha)$ such that ν is a S-b-shading of A.
18. For any $\alpha \varepsilon L \setminus \{0\}$ and each γ -open α -shading μ open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is an S- β_α -cover of A.
19. For any $\alpha \varepsilon L \setminus \{0\}$ and each γ -open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is α β_α -cover of A.
20. For any $\alpha \varepsilon L \setminus \{0\}$ and and γ -open S- β_α -cover μ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon L$ with $\alpha \varepsilon \beta(b)$ such that ν is an S- β_α -cover of A.
21. For any $\alpha \varepsilon L \setminus \{0\}$ and any countably γ -open S- β_α -cover μ of A, there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \varepsilon L$ with $\alpha \varepsilon \beta(b)$ such that ν is α S- β_α -cover of A.
22. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$, each γ -open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is an S- β_α -cover of A.
23. For any $\alpha \varepsilon M(L)$, each γ -open S- β_α -cover μ of A has a subfamily which is α β_α -cover of A.

24. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ and any γ -open $S\text{-}\beta_\alpha$ -cover μ of A , there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \in M(L)$ with $\alpha \in \beta^*(b)$ such that ν is an $S\text{-}\beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
25. For any $\alpha \in M(L)$ and any γ -open $S\text{-}\beta_\alpha$ -cover μ of A , there exist a countable subfamily ν of μ and $b \in M(L)$ with $\alpha \in \beta^*(b)$ such that ν is $\alpha \beta_\alpha$ cover of A .
26. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -open Q_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is αQ_b cover of A .
27. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -open Q_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is αQ_b cover of A .
28. For any $\alpha \in L \setminus \{0\}$ and any $b \in \beta(\alpha) \setminus \{0\}$, each γ -open Q_α -cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is $\alpha S\text{-}\beta_b$ cover of A .
29. For any $A \in M(L)$, and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each γ -open Q_α cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is a Q_b cover of A .
30. For any $A \in M(L)$ and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each γ -open Q_α cover μ of A has a countable subfamily which is a Q_b cover of A .
31. For any $A \in M(L)$ and any $b \in \beta^*(\alpha)$ each countably γ open Q_α cover μ of A has a finite subfamily which is a $S\text{-}\beta_b$ cover of A .

Lemma 3.14: Let $(X, \omega_L(T))$ be generated by (X, τ) . If A is an γ -open L -set in (X, τ) , then X_A is an γ -open set in $(X, \omega_L(T))$. If B is an γ -open L -set in $(X, \omega_L(T))$, then $B_{(a)}$ is an γ -open set in (X, τ) for every $a \in L$.
 Proof. This is easy to prove if one notices that $X_{D^c} = (X_D)^c$ and $X_{D_0^c} = (X_D)^c$ and $X_{D_0} = (X_D)_0$ and applies Lemma 5.4 in [9].

Theorem 3.15: Let (X, τ) be a topological space and $(X, \omega_L(T))$ be generated by (X, τ) . Then $(X, \omega_L(T))$ is countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof) if and only if (X, τ) is countably γ -compact (γ -Lindelof).

Proof: We only prove that the theorem is true for countable γ -compactness. Let μ be a countable γ -open cover of (X, τ) .

Then $\{X_A | A \in \mu\}$ is a family of γ -open L -sets in $(X, \omega_L(T))$ with $\bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{A \in \mu} X_A(x) = 1$. From countable γ -compactness of $(X, \omega_L(T))$, we have that $1 = \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{A \in \mu} X_A(x) \leq \bigvee_{v \in 2^\mu} \bigwedge_{A \in v} X_A(x)$. This implies that there exists

$v \in 2^{(\mu)}$ such that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{A \in v} X_A(x) = 1$. Hence v is a cover of (X, τ) . Therefore (X, τ) is countable γ -compact.

Conversely, let μ be a countable family of γ -open L -sets in $(X, \omega_L(T))$ and $\bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x) = a$. If $a = 0$,

obviously we have that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in \mu} B(x) \leq \bigvee_{v \in 2^{(\mu)}} \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x)$. Now we suppose that $a \neq 0$. In this case, for any $b \in \beta(a)$

By lemma 3.14, this implies that $\{B(b) | B \in \mu\}$ is a countable γ -open cover of (X, τ) and from the countable γ -compactness of (X, τ) we know that there exists $v \in 2^{(\mu)}$ such that $\{B(b) | B \in v\}$ is a cover of (X, τ) .

Hence $b \leq \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x)$.

Moreover, we have that $b \leq \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x) \leq \bigvee_{v \in 2^{(\mu)}} \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x)$.

This implies that $\bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x) = a = v \{b | b \in \beta(a)\} \leq \bigvee_{v \in 2^{(\mu)}} \bigwedge_{x \in X} \bigvee_{B \in v} B(x)$.

Therefore $(X, \omega_L(T))$ is countable γ -compact.

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